

A MULTIDIMENSIONAL APPROACH TO STUDY THE EVOLUTION OF THE SCHOOL POPULATION AND THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF AN URBAN SYSTEM

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Abstract

Some equations that are a generalization of the reaction-diffusion models written in finite-differences form are introduced. They offer the possibility of relating all the spatial parts of a system, (not only neighbor ones) that is, districts in a city, areas in an ecosystem, etc., as well as to consider other dimension-variables, besides time and space, in dynamical models of complex systems. A general methodology for constructing such kind of systems is suggested.

The mentioned equations and methodology are applied to study the evolution of the quality of life and the school population of an urban system per districts as a consequence of a concrete decision of the city council.

Keywords: Urban model, complex system, dynamic system, space-time system, multidimensional system, quality of life, school needs.

Introduction

Our starting point is the multidimensional dynamical models based on the equations that we provide in our last publications (Micó & Caselles, 1998, for instance). These equations are a generalization of the reaction-diffusion models written in finite-differences form. That generalization consists of the possibility of putting into relationship all the spatial parts of a system, that is, districts in a city, areas in an ecosystem, etc. In addition, these equations are useful for introducing the space-variables and other possible dimension-variables in the models of Systems Dynamics, which enables us to construct space-time or multidimensional models of complex systems.

Moreover, we provide a general methodology for building space-time or multidimensional models of this kind of systems. Our main aim is to use this methodology and the previously cited multidimensional model to study the evolution of the quality of life and the

school population of an urban system per districts. In order to do this; on the one hand, the quality of life per districts is quantified by using the *perceived-image* variable, which is computed by depending on environmental and housing needs. On the other hand, the school needs per districts are computed by defining the *difference-variable* between the *school population* variable and the *school places* variable in each period of time and for each district.

Nevertheless, the main found problem has been the computation of the migration of population between districts, which has been solved by supposing that this migration is directly proportional to the difference between districts of the perceived-image variable. This hypothesis provides us results, for the state-variables, close to the real ones. This fact leads us to consider the model as being validated.

Some simulations are made with the model, under different values of the scenario-variables, using the database of a city, in Spain. These simulations are determined in order to study the evolution

of the schooling needs and the quality of life per districts in the urban system, as well as other important variables such as population per cohorts or housing needs.

The studied application case is an adaptation of a preceding model useful only for one district or zone (Ferrer & Caselles, 1994).

Theoretical background

The *multidimensional mathematical model* (or *MMM* for short) (Micó & Caselles, 1998) (Micó, Caselles, Soler & Ferrer, 1999) is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}(t, \bar{\rho}) = & \bar{w}(t-dt, \bar{\rho}) + \bar{f}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{w}(t-dt, \bar{\rho}), \bar{b}(t, \bar{\rho}), t, \bar{\rho}) + \\ & + \sum_{\bar{p}' \neq \bar{p}} \bar{h}_{\bar{p}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{p} \leftarrow \bar{p}') - \sum_{\bar{p}' \neq \bar{p}} \bar{h}_{\bar{p}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{p} \rightarrow \bar{p}') + \\ & + \left(\sum_{\bar{x}' \neq \bar{x}} \bar{h}_{\bar{x}'}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{x} \leftarrow \bar{x}') - \sum_{\bar{x}' \neq \bar{x}} \bar{h}_{\bar{x}'}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{x} \rightarrow \bar{x}') \right) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), $\bar{f}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{w}(t-dt, \bar{\rho}), \bar{b}(t, \bar{\rho}), t, \bar{\rho})$ is the vector of *time-rates* between instants $t-dt$ and t , that depends: firstly, on a vector of state-variables, $\bar{w}(t-dt, \bar{\rho})$, secondly, on a vector of input-variables $\bar{b}(t, \bar{\rho})$ that, in the most general case, can be functions of all the change-variables and finally, it can also depend explicitly on time t and on the restricted-change-vector $\bar{\rho} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m)$. With the time-rates, we compute the variation of state-variables when the other change-variables, given by the vector $\bar{\rho}$, keep constant. Sometimes, the change-vector $\bar{r} = (t, x_1, \dots, x_m)$ can be used formally for the sake of simplicity.

On the other hand, in Equation (1), $\bar{h}_{\bar{p}}$ and $\bar{h}_{\bar{x}}$, are the *multidimensional-rates*. Particularly, vectors $\bar{h}_{\bar{p}}$ are the *space-time rates* and they represent the variation of state-variables through the diffusion between spatial parts of the system and between the instants $t-dt$ and t . The other multidimensional rates, $\bar{h}_{\bar{x}}$, represent the

variation of state-variables between different values, \bar{x} and \bar{x}' , of each change-variable and between the instants $t-dt$ and t . In both cases, we have introduced, firstly, the positive multidimensional-rates, $\bar{h}_{\bar{p}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{p} \leftarrow \bar{p}')$ and $\bar{h}_{\bar{x}'}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{x} \leftarrow \bar{x}')$, that increase the value of the state-variables at each value of the change-variables, \bar{p} and x_i respectively, and secondly, the negative multidimensional-rates, $\bar{h}_{\bar{p}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{p} \rightarrow \bar{p}')$ and $\bar{h}_{\bar{x}'}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{x} \rightarrow \bar{x}')$, that decrease the value of the state-variables at each value of the change-variables \bar{p} and x_i respectively.

Furthermore, positive and negative multidimensional-rates are not independent: the decrease given by the rates $\bar{h}_{\bar{p}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{p} \rightarrow \bar{p}')$ or $\bar{h}_{\bar{x}'}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{x} \rightarrow \bar{x}')$ are equal to the increase given by the rates $\bar{h}_{\bar{p}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{p}' \leftarrow \bar{p})$ or $\bar{h}_{\bar{x}'}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{x}' \leftarrow \bar{x})$, respectively. Therefore, we can write:

$$\bar{h}_{\bar{p}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{p} \rightarrow \bar{p}') = \bar{h}_{\bar{p}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{p}' \leftarrow \bar{p}) \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{h}_{\bar{x}'}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{x} \rightarrow \bar{x}') = \bar{h}_{\bar{x}'}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{x}' \leftarrow \bar{x}) \quad (3)$$

These last identities avoid us to compute the negative multidimensional-

rates, because they are computed through the positive multidimensional-rates. If we

substitute them in Equation (1), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}(t, \bar{\rho}) = & \bar{w}(t - dt, \bar{\rho}) + \bar{f}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{w}(t - dt, \bar{\rho}), \bar{b}(t, \bar{\rho}), t, \bar{\rho}) + \\ & + \sum_{\bar{p}' \neq \bar{p}} (\bar{h}_{\bar{p}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{p} \leftarrow \bar{p}') - \bar{h}_{\bar{p}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{p}' \leftarrow \bar{p})) \\ & + \sum_{\bar{x}' \neq \bar{x}} (\bar{h}_{\bar{x}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{x} \leftarrow \bar{x}') - \bar{h}_{\bar{x}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{x}' \leftarrow \bar{x})) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) is another representation of Equation (1) and also defines the *multidimensional mathematical model (MMM)*, which is the main equation in order to construct *multidimensional dynamical models* (or *MDM* for short). The process for obtaining entirely a MDM from the equation that defines the MMM is given by the methodology described in the following section, and its goal consists of finding the explicit dependencies of time and the multidimensional rates on state-variables and on input-variables. These dependencies can be direct or indirect and can be defined through auxiliary variables.

Then, as a conclusion, once an entire MDM is built, it is defined by all input, auxiliary and state-variables, and by all functional relations between these variables, mainly by the MMM, through which it is possible to generate all the MDM.

Finally, two important features characterize the MDM. On the one hand, the models of cellular automata (Wolfram, 1986) can be seen as particular cases of it (Micó & Caselles, 1998). On the other hand, the MDM can be also seen as a generalization of the Systems Dynamics models (Aracil, 1992), in order to introduce the space-variables and other change-variables into them (Micó & Caselles, 1998).

Methodology for constructing multidimensional dynamical models

We summarize here the methodology proposed by Micó, Caselles, Soler & Ferrer (1999) for the sake of constructing a multidimensional dynamical model. Its life cycle includes the following steps:

Step 1: Define all the state-variables that are going to describe formally the real system w_1, w_2, \dots, w_s . These variables must describe the basic features connected with the goal stated for the model, or with the *target of the modeling process*.

Step 2: State all change-variables such that state-variables depend on them, including time. If $\bar{r} = (t, x_1, \dots, x_m)$ is the change-vector that contains all of them, we can define the state-variables as the scalar fields $w_1(\bar{r}), w_2(\bar{r}), \dots, w_s(\bar{r})$.

Step 3: State the hypothesis that, in order to construct the multidimensional dynamical model, the basic equation is given by Equations (1) or (4), from which we compute the state-variables of the system.

Step 4: Find the functional relationships between time, multidimensional-rates, state-variables and input-variables, given by the following Equations:

$$\bar{f}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{w}(t - dt, \bar{\rho}), \bar{b}(t, \bar{\rho}), t, \bar{\rho}) = \bar{F}(\bar{w}(t - dt, \bar{\rho}), \bar{b}(t, \bar{\rho}), t, \bar{\rho}) \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{h}_{\bar{p}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{p} \leftarrow \bar{p}') = \bar{G}(\bar{w}(t - dt, \bar{p}), \bar{w}(t - dt, \bar{p}'), \bar{b}(t, \bar{p}), t, \bar{p}) \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{h}_{\bar{x}}^{t-dt \rightarrow t}(\bar{x} \leftarrow \bar{x}') = \bar{H}(\bar{w}(t - dt, \bar{x}), \bar{w}(t - dt, \bar{x}'), \bar{b}(t, \bar{x}), t, \bar{x}) \quad (7)$$

We will look for these functions by defining the necessary auxiliary variables, by finding regression relationships from databases, by requesting expert opinions, etc.

Step 5: Validate the model. The validation process is frequently performed by comparing model results with historic values of the state-variables, taking into account the initial conditions for the state-variables and the history of the input-variables. This kind of performance assumes the stability of the structure and behavior of the system.

Step 6: Use the validated model for finding, by simulation, the values of control input-variables that produce the values of state-variables that best fit their respective goal. Stating available strategies (values of control-variables along time) might perform this simulation process under possible scenarios (values of uncontrollable input-variables along time). Feedback from any step to any previous one is frequent, as a consequence of verification and validation.

Application case

This application case consists of building a MDM of an urban system in order to study the evolution of the quality of life and the school population per districts inside it. On the one hand, the “quality of life” (Caselles, 1992) per districts is quantified by using the *perceived-image* variable, which is computed as a linear combination of environmental and housing parameters, as we can see in the following. On the other hand, the school needs per districts are computed through the *difference-variable* between the *school population* variable and the *school places* variable in each period of time and for each district.

The model has been obtained following the methodology described in the last section. Thus, all the input and auxiliary-variables are defined as a consequence of the present state-variables and the equations supplied by the MMM. Nevertheless, in order that the model can be better understood, we firstly provide the description of all variables of the model.

NUCO Number of population cohorts

NUNE Number of levels of school places

NUCN Number of kinds of school places (the kind depending of financial support)

NUIN Number of kinds of infrastructures (housing; commercial premises; etc.)

NUDX Number of longitudes

NUDY Number of latitudes

YMAI Initial value of the perceived good image index of the district (NUDX;NUDY)

POBI Initial population per cohorts and districts (NUCO;NUDX;NUDY)

PESI Number of initial school places per levels, kinds, and districts (NUNE;NUCN;NUDX;NUDY)

SCOI Initial number of infrastructures: housing; commercial premises; etc.) per districts (NUIN;NUDX;NUDY)

SOCI Initial number of occupied infrastructures per districts (NUIN;NUDX;NUDY)

TDIF Diffusion rate of population between districts

TNAC Birth rate per thousand

XACO Number of years of each population cohort except last one (NUCO-1)

RPOC Weights corresponding to secondary and professional school (2)

CPES Construction of school places per levels and kinds (NUNE;NUCN)

DPES Demolition of school places per levels and kinds (NUNE;NUCN)

XEMI Number of emigrants

XINM Number of immigrants

TDEF Death rate per thousand per cohorts (NUCO)

POEM Maximum reachable school population

PLEM Maximum reachable school places

TRET Smooth time for the image perception of the district

PHOT Ratio of 5* hotel places with respect to its maximum

TREX Actual output traffic with respect to its maximum

PCON Weights corresponding to pollution (NUIN+2)

PTRA Weights corresponding to traffic (NUIN+3)

PRUI Weights corresponding to noise (NUIN+2)
PHAC Weights corresponding to crowding (NUIN+1)
PIMA Weights corresponding to city image (NUIN+5)
PCOS Programs of infrastructures construction (NUIN)
CMAx Maximum construction of infrastructures (NUIN)
PERV Average number of persons per housing
POBL Population per cohorts and districts (NUCO;NUDX;NUDY)
DIFE Population immigration per cohorts between districts (NUCO;NUDX;NUDY;NUDX;NUDY)
DIFS Population emigration per cohorts between districts (NUCO;NUDX;NUDY;NUDX;NUDY)
POBA Population per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
POBE Population per cohorts (NUCO)
PESC School places per levels, kinds and districts (NUNE;NUCN;NUDX;NUDY)
CPEM Construction of school places per levels, kinds and districts (NUNE;NUCN;NUDX;NUDY)
DPEM Demolition of school places per levels, kinds and districts (NUNE;NUCN;NUDX;NUDY)
POMM Maximum reachable school population per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
PLMM Maximum reachable school places per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
SCON Number of infrastructures per districts (NUIN;NUDX;NUDY)
SOCU Number of occupied infrastructures per districts (NUIN;NUDX;NUDY)
CREC Births and increasing population per cohorts and districts (NUCO;NUDX;NUDY)
POBT Total population
POEC School population per levels and districts (NUNE;NUDX;NUDY)
PEST Total school places per levels and districts (NUNE;NUDX;NUDY)
BACA Number of vacant school places per levels and districts (NUNE;NUDX;NUDY)
EMIG Emigrants per cohorts and districts (NUCO;NUDX;NUDY)
YNMI Immigrants per cohorts and districts (NUCO;NUDX;NUDY)
DEFU Deaths per cohorts and districts (NUCO;NUDX;NUDY)
POES Total school population per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
PLES Total school places per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
CONA Index of pollution per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
RUID Index of noises per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
YMAG Index of good image of each district (NUDX;NUDY)
TRAF Index of traffic per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
HACI Index of crowding per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
YMAP Index of the perceived good image for the district (NUDX;NUDY)
YMAT Global Index of the perceived good image
CCON Number of infrastructures construction per district (NUIN;NUDX;NUDY)
TCON Rate of infrastructures construction per district (NUIN;NUDX;NUDY)
TOCL Rate of infrastructures occupation per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
COCU Number of infrastructures occupation per districts (NUIN;NUDX;NUDY)
OCUP Coefficient of infrastructures occupation per districts (NUIN;NUDX;NUDY)
DCON Number of infrastructures demolition per districts (NUIN;NUDX;NUDY)
TDEM Rate of infrastructures demolition or leaving per districts (NUIN;NUDX;NUDY)
TDEL Rate of commercial premises leaving per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
DOCU Number of housing and commercial premises leaving per districts (NUIN;NUDX;NUDY)
TCO1 Rate of housing construction per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
TCO2 Rate of commercial premises construction per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
TDE1 Rate of housing demolition or leaving per districts (NUDX;NUDY)
TDE2 Rate of commercial premises demolition or leaving per districts (NUDX;NUDY)

For this list, the variables in brackets represent the range of variability of the corresponding change-variables that the described variable depends on. For example, *tde2* depend on x and y , being $1 \leq x \leq nudx$ and $1 \leq y \leq nudy$.

Following the previously mentioned methodology, for step 1, the defined state-variables of the model are *pobl*, *pesc*,

ymap, *socu* and *scon*, and *pobi*, *pesi*, *ymai*, *soci* and *scoi*, are their corresponding initial conditions. For step 2, and observing the list of variables, the variability ranges of the change-variables are the following: $1 \leq x \leq nudx$; $1 \leq y \leq nudy$; $1 \leq p \leq nuco$; $1 \leq q \leq nune$; $1 \leq r \leq nucn$; $1 \leq s \leq nuin$. Moreover, in the given list, from *nuco* to *perv* they are input-variables and all other

ones are auxiliary-variables. Thus, for step 3, the equations that define the MMM for

each state-variable are the following:

$$pobl(t,p,x,y) = pobl(t-dt,p,x,y) - defu(t,p,x,y) + crec(t,p,x,y) - cred(t,p,x,y) + ynmi(t,p,x,y) - emig(t,p,x,y) + \sum_{(x',y') \neq (x,y)} [dife(t,p,(x,y) \leftarrow (x',y')) - difs(t,p,(x,y) \rightarrow (x',y'))] \quad (8.1)$$

$$pesc(t,q,r,x,y) = pesc(t-dt,q,r,x,y) + cpem(t,q,r,x,y) - dpem(t,q,r,x,y) \quad (8.2)$$

$$ymap(t,x,y) = ymap(t-dt,x,y) + (ymag(t,x,y) - ymap(t-dt,x,y)) / tret \quad (8.3)$$

$$socu(t,s,x,y) = socu(t-dt,s,x,y) + cocu(t,s,x,y) - docu(t,s,x,y) \quad (8.4)$$

$$scon(t,s,x,y) = scon(t-dt,s,x,y) + ccon(t,s,x,y) - dcon(t,s,x,y) \quad (8.5)$$

Note that, in these last equations, it is possible, through their formal expression, to identify the time rates, which are *defu*, *crec*, *cred*, *ynmi*, *emig*, *cpem*, *dpem*, *cocu*, *docu*, *ccon* and *dcon*, while the

multidimensional rates are *dife* and *difs*. Finally, following step 4, we write the other equations of the MDM for the urban system:

$$POMM \quad pommm(t,x,y) = poem(t) \cdot poba(t,x,y) / pobt(t)$$

$$PLMM \quad plmm(t,x,y) = plem(t) \cdot poba(t,x,y) / pobt(t)$$

$$CPEM \quad cpem(t,q,r,x,y) = cpes(t,q,r) \cdot poba(t,x,y) / pobt(t)$$

$$DPEM \quad dpem(t,q,r,x,y) = dpes(t,q,r) \cdot poba(t,x,y) / pobt(t)$$

$$POBT \quad pobt(t) = \sum_{(p,x,y)} pobl(t-dt,p,x,y)$$

$$POBE \quad pobe(t,p) = \sum_{(x,y)} pobl(t-dt,p,x,y)$$

$$EMIG \quad emig(t,p,x,y) = xemig(t) \cdot pobl(t-dt,p,x,y) / pobt(t)$$

$$YNMI \quad ynmi(t,p,x,y) = xinm(t) \cdot (pobe(t,p) / pobt(t)) \cdot (ymai(t,x,y) / ymat(t))$$

$$POBA \quad poba(t,x,y) = \sum_{(p)} pobl(t-dt,p,x,y)$$

$$DEFU \quad defu(t,p,x,y) = pobl(t-dt,p,x,y) \cdot tdef(t,p) / 1000$$

$$OCUP \quad ocup(t,s,x,y) = socu(t-dt,s,x,y) / scon(t-dt,s,x,y)$$

$$CREC \quad crec(t,1,x,y) = poba(t,x,y) \cdot tnac(t) / 1000$$

$$crec(t,1 < p < nuco, x, y) = pobl(t-dt, p-1, x, y) / xaco(p-1) + (pobl(t-dt, p, x, y) / xaco(p) - pobl(t-dt, p-1, x, y) / xaco(p-1)) \cdot xaco(p-1) / (xaco(p-1) + xaco(p))$$

$$crec(t, nuco, x, y) = pobl(t-dt, nuco-1, x, y) / xaco(nuco-1) + (pobl(t-dt, nuco-1, x, y) / xaco(nuco-1) - pobl(t-dt, nuco-2, x, y) / xaco(nuco-2)) \cdot xaco(nuco-1) / (xaco(nuco-2) + xaco(nuco-1))$$

$$CRED \quad cred(t, 1 \leq p < nuco, x, y) = cred(t, p+1, x, y)$$

$$cred(t, nuco, x, y) = 0$$

$$PEST \quad pest(t,q,x,y) = \sum_{(r)} pesc(t,q,r,x,y)$$

$$HACI \quad haci(t,x,y) = \sum_{(1 \leq s \leq nuin)} phac(s) \cdot ocup(t,s,x,y) + phac(nuin+1) \cdot phot(t)$$

$$DIFE \quad \text{if } (x,y) = (x',y') \vee ymap(t-dt,x,y) \leq ymap(t-dt,x',y') :$$

$$dife(t,x,y,x',y') = 0$$

$$\text{if } (x,y) \neq (x',y') \wedge ymap(t-dt,x,y) > ymap(t-dt,x',y') :$$

$$dife(t,p,x,y,x',y') = tdif(ymap(t-dt,x,y) - ymap(t-dt,x',y')) \cdot pobl(t-dt,p,x',y')$$

$$DIFS \quad difs(t,p,x,y,x',y') = dife(t,p,x',y',x,y)$$

$$PLES \quad ples(t,x,y) = \sum_{(q)} pest(t,q,x,y)$$

$$OPEC \quad poec(t, 1 \leq q < nune-1, x, y) = pobl(t, p+1, x, y)$$

$$poec(t, nune-1, x, y) = pobl(t, p+1, x, y) \cdot rpoc(1)$$

$$poec(t, nune, x, y) = pobl(t, p+1, x, y) \cdot rpoc(2)$$

$$BACA \quad baca(t,q,x,y) = pest(t,q,x,y) - poec(t,q,x,y)$$

$$POES \quad poes(t,x,y) = \sum_{(q)} poec(t,q,x,y)$$

$$TRAF \quad traf(t,x,y) = \sum_{(s)} ptras(s) \cdot ocup(t,s,x,y) + ptras(nuin+1) \cdot phot +$$

$$ptras(nuin+2) \cdot poes(t,x,y) / pommm(t,x,y) +$$

$$ptras(nuin+3) \cdot ples(t,x,y) / plmm(t,x,y) + tret$$

$$CONA \quad cona(t,x,y) = \sum_{(s)} pcon(s) \cdot ocup(t,s,x,y) + pcon(nuin+1) \cdot traf(t,x,y) +$$

$$pcon(nuin+2) \cdot phot$$

$$RUID \quad ruid(t,x,y) = \sum_{(s)} pruis(s) \cdot ocup(t,s,x,y) + pruis(nuin+1) \cdot traf(t,x,y) +$$

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prui (nuin+2) · poes (t,x,y) / pomm (t,x,y)
YMAG ymag (t,x,y) = [Σ(s) pima (s) ocup (t,s,x,y) + pima (nuin+3) · phot] / 2 + 0.5 +
[ pima (nuin+1) · haci (t,x,y) + pima (nuin+2)
traf (t,x,y) + pima (nuin+4) · cona (t,x,y) + pima (nuin+5)
ruid (t,x,y) ] / 2 + 0.5
YMAT ymat = Σ(x,y) ymap (t-dt,x,y)
TCON tcon (t,1,x,y) = tco1 (t,x,y) · tcon (t,2,x,y) = tco2 (t,x,y)
COCU cocu (t,1,x,y) = (crec (t,1,x,y) + Σ(p,x',y') dife (t,p,x,y,x',y') +
Σ(p) ynmi (t,p,x,y)) / perv ; cocu (t,2,x,y) = tocl (t,x,y) · socu (t-
dt,2,x,y) / 1000
TDEM tdem (t,1,x,y) = tdel (t,x,y) ; tdem (t,2,x,y) = tde2 (t,x,y)
DOCU docu (t,1x,y) = ( Σ(p,x',y') difs (t,p,x,y,x',y') + Σ(p) defu (t,p,x,y) +
Σ(p) emig (t,p,x,y)) / perv
docu (t,2,x,y) = tdel (t,x,y) · socu (t-dt,2,x,y) / 1000
CCON if (scon (t-dt,s,x,y) + ccon (t,s,x,y)) ≤ cmax (t,s) :
ccon (t,s,x,y) = tcon (t,s,x,y) · scon (t-dt,s,x,y) / 1000
+ pcos (t,s)
if (scon (t-dt,s,x,y) + ccon (t,s,x,y)) > cmax (t,s) :
ccon (t,s,x,y) = cmax (t,s) - scon (t-dt,s,x,y)
DCON dcon (t,s,x,y) = tdem (t,s,x,y) · scon (t-dt,s,x,y) / 1000
TOCL tocl (t,x,y) = f1 (ymap (t,x,y))
{(0.1,1), (0.2,1.2), (0.3,2), (0.4,3), (0.5,4), (0.6,4.7),
(0.7,5.2), (0.8,5.6), (0.9,5.9), (1,6)}
TDEL tdel (t,x,y) = f2 (ymap (t,x,y))
{(0.1,14), (0.2,10), (0.3,8), (0.4,7.5), (0.5,7), (0.6,6.2),
(0.7,5.6), (0.8,5.3), (0.9,5.1), (1,5)}
TCO1 tco1 (t,x,y) = f3 (ymap (t,x,y))
{(0.1,1), (0.2,1.5), (0.3,3), (0.4,5), (0.5,8), (0.6,9.5),
(0.7,11), (0.8,12), (0.9,12.1), (1,12.2)}
TCO2 tco2 (t,x,y) = f4 (ymap (t,x,y))
{(0.1,1), (0.2,1.5), (0.3,3), (0.4,5), (0.5,8), (0.6,9.5),
(0.7,11), (0.8,12), (0.9,12.1), (1,12.2)}
TDE1 tdel (t,x,y) = f5 (ymap (t,x,y))
{(0.1,10), (0.2,7), (0.3,4.5), (0.4,2.5), (0.5,1.1),
(0.6,1), (0.7,0.95), (0.8,0.9), (0.9,0.85), (1,0.8)}
TDE2 tde2 (t,x,y) = f6 (ymap (t,x,y))
{(0.1,10), (0.2,7), (0.3,4.5), (0.4,2.5), (0.5,1.1),
(0.6,1), (0.7,0.95), (0.8,0.9), (0.9,0.85), (1,0.8)}

```

Rates and auxiliary-variables can be computed with this list of functions. Functions *f1*, *f2*, *f3*, *f4*, *f5* and *f6* are given by tables of experimental sets of points. Observe that they are global relations independent of the districts represented by (x,y).

The next step consists of validate the model by comparing the historical values of the state-variables with the results given by the model for the same period.

Validation and simulations

The validation process has been performed by contrasting past predictions

against historical data referred to the city as a whole, because there are no available historical data about migration between districts that is adequate for validating the model when it is desegregated per districts. Therefore, the diffusion rate of population between districts has been adjusted by calibration.

In order to design a simulation plan, it is necessary to classify the variables of the model into the following categories: parameters, control variables, scenario variables, initial values of state variables, state variables, auxiliary variables, and strict output variables. Let us see it.

- Input variables: data input for the model.
 - Parameters: supposedly being uncontrollable constants in the considered case.
Nuco, nune, nucn, nuin, nudx, nudy, tdif, xaco, cpes, dpes, tdef, poem, plem, tret, pcon, ptra, prui, phac, pima, cmax.
 - Control variables: supposedly being controllable by the user of the model.
Phot, pcos.
 - Scenario variables: uncontrollable variables supposedly being associated with possible situations of the environment (scenarios).
Tnac, rpoc, xemi, xinm, trex, perv.
 - Initial values for state variables.
Ymai, pobi, pesi, scoi, soci.
- Output variables: results produced by the model.
 - State variables: those requiring an initial value for being calculated.
Pobl, pesc, scon, socu, ymag.
 - Auxiliary variables: those being intermediate steps in a process of calculus.
Dife, difs, poba, pobe, cpem, dpem, pomm, plmm, crec, pobt, poec, Pest, emig, ynmi, defu, poes, ples, cona, ruid, traf, haci, ymap, ccon, Tcon, tocl, cocu, ocup, tcon, tocl, cocu, ocup, dcon, tdem, tdel, docu, Tco1, tco2, tde1, tde2.
 - Strict output variables: those that do not influence any other one.
Baca, ymat.

The simulation plan to be designed derives from the necessity of deciding about the destination of a given ground plot, choosing between two options: the first one, a five stars hotel and a building including housing and commercial premises; and the second one, a school building. Supposedly the city council has

to authorize one of these options, taking into account the future necessity of school places and the impact of such options over the “quality of life” in the different districts and in the whole city. All relevant variables are assumed as being present in the model.

Three scenarios are considered as sufficient:

- Positive scenario.
Tnac, and *xinm/xemi* are increasing (births and immigration movements rising).
Perv (persons per housing) and *trex* (exogenous traffic) also are increasing.
Rpoc (% of people studying) keeps constant at present level.
- Negative scenario.
Tnac, and *xinm/xemi* balance are slightly descending.
Perv (persons per housing) keeps constant.
Trex (exogenous traffic) descends.
Rpoc (% of people studying) is very slightly descending.
- Scenario following tendency.
Tnac keeps stable at present level. *Xemi* and *xinm* are in equilibrium.
Perv (persons per housing) and *trex* (exogenous traffic) increase slightly.
Rpoc (% of people studying) increase slightly.

Two “control strategies” are tested in combinations with the three considered scenarios: Strategy one: to construct the

projected buildings, giving the corresponding values to *phot* and *pcos*. Strategy two: to keep the ground plot free,

giving to *phot* and *pcos* the values following tendency.

Results with concrete numerical data show that, weighting probabilistically the three considered scenarios, the school needs (negative *baca*) do not increase in the future and the impact of the projected buildings over the image of the district (*ymap*) and over the image of the city (*yamat*) is positive. Consequently the project can be authorized under the considered assumptions.

Concluding remarks

Equations (1) and (4) are a generalization of the reaction-diffusion models written in finite-differences form. They offer the possibility of relating all the spatial parts of a system, (not only neighbor ones) that is, districts in a city, areas in an ecosystem, etc., as well as to consider other dimension-variables, besides time and space, in dynamical models. This feature enables us to construct space-time or multidimensional models of complex systems. A general methodology for constructing such kind of systems is suggested.

The mentioned equations and methodology are applied to study the evolution of the quality of life and the school population of an urban system per districts as a consequence of a concrete decision of the city council. This decision consists of authorizing or not the construction of a hotel, housing and some commercial premises in a plot for which an alternative destination could be to construct more school places. Both strategies are simulated with three different scenarios in the multidimensional model and the resulting decision has been justified.

The main problem found in the validation process has been the computation of the migration of population between districts, due to the non-existence of adequate historical data. The hypothesis that this migration is directly proportional

to the difference between districts with respect to its respective perceived image provides us results, for the state-variables, close to the real ones. This fact leads us to consider the model as being validated.

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